

ARDC Infrastructure discovery report - Global experiences digital research infrastructure federations

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October 2019, version 1.0

Project Summary

Monash University received Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) infrastructure discovery funding to lead a global site visit tour themed "Global experiences digital research infrastructure federations". A panel consisting of three primary members, three collaborating discovery project members and two International members participated in on-site interviews at 16 sites across the UK, EU and USA.

The sites spanned an orthogonal set of approaches to digital infrastructure – domain-agnostic *traditional* computing centres and emerging *domain-specific* digital initiatives. Traditional computing sites (such as High Performance Computing (HPC) / High Throughput Computing (HTC) centres, clouds, eResearch centres, etc. across the Tier-1 and Tier-2 spectrum) differentiate from commercial clouds by hosting research-driven hardware at scale. They are not historically federated but increasingly participate in some form of cross-site computing. Whereas domain-specific digital initiatives tend to be distributed research-driven soft infrastructure (platforms), with a focus on scaling-out the number of users.

The Nectar Research Cloud has straddled these two orthogonal directions. It is internationally renowned as novel and emerging hard infrastructure that is also federated (distributed), supporting many research digital platforms. For this discovery exercise we deemphasise the ambiguous notion of *cloud*, and instead describe the intent as software defined infrastructure driven by research. So what makes the tuple of hard and federated digital infrastructure impactful? What adjustments could be made to further exploit the Research Cloud for the trend towards domain-led infrastructure? To answer these questions we asked each site - what does digital research infrastructure federation mean? What is the governance between co-design/operation, capacity & funding? Six themes emerged from our consultations:

- Domains expect more than cloud in the federation
- World-class sites are multi-modal & multi-domain
- Research infrastructure programs are still investing
- Sensitive / confidential data & GDPR
- Core services increasing quality services the role of promulgating
- The world reveres the ecosystem we have

Project Goal

The national OpenStack federation (the ARDC Nectar / Australian Research Cloud) has been an outstanding success. It has received accolades as a global innovator. World-leading digital research infrastructures regularly state they have learnt from Nectar. There is a general consensus it is a cloud. We also understand it is a federation of digital research infrastructure. There is a sense that it fits IT term multi-cloud, however the term fails to entirely capture the role and value. As part of a researcher's instrument or tool, the Research Cloud serves the role of enabling horizontal federation (*at the bottom* – it is underpinning, domain agnostic, and removes barriers to collaborate across organisations). The Research Cloud achieved infrastructure scale, by attracting co-investment from jurisdictionally distinct regions. It achieved user scale by enabling accelerated access to early forms of cloud-nativeness. It also achieved scale by powering domain-specific platforms, which in turn attract scale of usage within a narrow domain. How does this set of properties compare to global trends?

To inform Australia's next generation of investment, we should learn what progress has been made elsewhere. Learning from global experiences intends to inform us, to keep us ahead.

The goal: to amass evidence from globally leading research infrastructures (across the spectrum of organisations including universities, research organisations, and communities), pertaining to:

- the meaning of digital federations,
- the role of digital federations, and
- the relationship between federation and impact.

To acquire this evidence, a small panel visited these globally leading research infrastructures, and interviewed staff associated with governance, architecture and communities.

Terms of reference used per site visit

Broadly speaking the ARDC is asking...

- what are the next major investments it should make, and
- what of the existing capabilities it should sustain

... to sustain an impactful research environment?

Language used in the consultations

Digital Research Infrastructure: We have assumed that the Research Cloud (including national/ARDC and local capacities), the coordinated Virtual Laboratories / Platforms and the informal domain-specific software-based platforms created atop of the Research Cloud, are evidence of research-driven digital infrastructure.

Federation: interviews and subsequent evidence principally investigated the tension between:

- Horizontal federation / Federate at the bottom (a network of legally distinct infrastructures operating the same underpinning cloud infrastructure), vs
- Vertical federation / Federate at the top (a network of legally distinct entities operating the same domain-specific Platform over potentially different clouds / infrastructures)

Cloud: The term *cloud* is conflated and confused. Moreover, the collective of visited sites cannot be defined as cloud providers or federated cloud providers. They each host cloud, HPC and / or data. Rather, these sites have research-led (increasingly software defined) research infrastructure, where the offerings and access is driven by research impact. This differentiates from the notion (for e.g.) of commercial cloud, where access is determined by price and the offering is a commercial decision.

In IT terms the key notions are devops and Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD). In research infrastructure terms this is digital infrastructure and covers HPC, HTC, clouds, data storage & repositories, and various forms of cyber infrastructure / Virtual Laboratories.

Process used in the consultations

All sites agreed to a seminal report of the findings, in the form of:

1. Published as Creative Commons, with all interviewees and panel as co-authors
2. Each site has a 1-2page summary (synopsis), with the structure:
 - a. *What does digital research infrastructure federation mean?*
 - b. *What is the governance/relationship between co-design/operation, capacity & funding?*
 - c. *Infrastructure at a glance*
 - d. *Noted lessons / observations*
3. A process where
 - a. the panel visited the site, and interviewed staff,
 - b. the panel create an initial draft synopsis of the site,
 - c. the site reviews and modifies the synopsis,
 - d. the chair creates a preamble, and
 - e. the panel collate and publish.

As the published findings is a collaboration involving 16 international sites, and the brevity of time frames of the project, the seminal creative commons report will not complete in time for the summit.

However, preliminary summary findings and a link to the completed site synopsis' are provided in this report. Where the panel observed messages of a contentious nature, we have taken the discretion to omit them from public documentation.

Composition of the panel

Members of touring panel included:

- **Dr Steve Quenette** of Monash University (panel chair, director of a university node of the Nectar Research Cloud, and deputy director of the Monash eResearch Centre),
- **Max Wilkinson** of the ARDC, and
- **Brendan Davey** of TPAC (acting director of a node of the Nectar Research Cloud).

An open call was made to all the Research Cloud nodes, with a noted preference for a node of different constitutional style (e.g. an incorporated node, given Monash is a university node). However, due to the compressed timeline no incorporated node could participate.

The tour attracted the self-funded participation with two other ARDC discovery projects. This includes:

- **Dr Wojtek Goscinski**, lead of the data focussed HPC facility (MASSIVE), and
- **Komathy Padmanabhan**

Both of whom are delivering the “*Machine learning infrastructure deployed at scale: understanding requirements, demand, impact and international best practice*” ARDC discovery project.

Additionally:

- **Anitha Kannan**, from the “*Developing a proposal for enabling the creation of health data collections and a federated secure platform for research collaborations over these collections of sensitive data*” ARDC discovery project.

Anitha and Komathy attended a subset of the sites.

The OpenStack Scientific Interest Group is the one global forum common to the majority of the sites, and in particular the Nectar Research Cloud. We offered an invitation to the SIG to attend where possible (at their own cost):

- **Stig Telfer**, chair of the OpenStack SIG
- **John Taylor**, delegate to Stig

Other institutions and discovery projects had engaged in the composition process. The main obstructions to further participation were budget, the compressed timelines, the desired calibre / role of participants and non-technical focus of conversation.

Approach to the composition of sites

Over a 16 day period the panel visited 13+ sites / infrastructures / networks, across 7 cities in the UK, EU and the USA.

The sites were invited to participate (host the panel) given the key message:

“We seek to gain some insight into the tensions and implementation rationale of ...

- *Federate at the bottom (a network of legally distinct infrastructures operating the same underpinning cloud infrastructure) vs federate at the top (a network of legally distinct entities operating the same domain-specific platform over potentially different clouds/infrastructure)*

... which is intertwined with other tensions our national community also discuss ...

- *Infrastructure-led vs discipline-led*
- *Institution-led vs centrally-led*
- *Simulation- vs data- science*
- *Data gravity- vs privacy*
- *Private- vs public- cloud*

The panel seeks to ensure ARDC have broad-stroke evidence of the environment necessary for many/all disciplines, knowing that in the Australian context, each discipline will dictate their own priorities.”

Given the shortness of time and resources, we targeted a few dominant domains such as: bioscience, imaging, physics and health / medical sciences. We also targeted sites that interact across the orthogonal vertical and horizontal axis. For example, CERN is the multi-modal horizontal site for high-energy physics, relative to WLCG as the global federation of high-energy physics sites, relative to IRIS as a UK participant into the WLCG (but at the same time its own federation). Another juncture is found with ELIXIR, EOSC-Life and EMBL-EBI's Embassy cloud. The third domain focus was public health / medical, where sensitivity to data has a significant influence on accessibility and subsequently the nature of federation.

We also targeted cross-discipline / tech-led technologies such as Kubernetes, AI, safe havens and OpenStack.

Towards a global seminal report on digital research infrastructure federations

The final site list in order of tour [host organisation / the research-led federation]:

- Swansea University / SAIL ([draft synopsis](#)),
- STFC / IRIS ([draft synopsis](#)),
- STFC - European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Pilot^γ,
- Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) ([draft synopsis](#)),
- STFC / Software Infrastructure Division (SID) ([draft synopsis](#)),
- EGI - European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Hub ([draft synopsis](#)),
- Elixir ([draft synopsis](#)),
- Cambridge Research Computing ([draft synopsis](#)),
- University College London (UCL) / Science Engineering South (SES) consortium & Thomas^λ,
- Swiss Personalized Health Network (SPHN) ([draft synopsis](#)),
- CERN ([draft synopsis](#)),
- Boston Partners / Accrual to Clinical Trials (ACT) using i2b2 and Shared Health Research Information Network (SHRINE) ([draft synopsis](#)),
- Boston Partners / CCDS^ξ,
- University of Michigan / SLATECI synopsis ([draft synopsis](#)),
- Penn State University^λ, and
- Indiana University / Jetstream ([draft synopsis](#))

As the process to publishing a whitepaper is not complete, all the synopses are denoted as draft. The drafts will be made available to ARDC staff on request. Four sites do not yet have a draft synopsis: (^λ) are effectively faculty – to – university scale HPC / eResearch centres and hence not prioritised for this report, (^ξ) similar but for machine learning in a health practice partnership, and (^γ) is not an infrastructure provider nor a domain, but rather, investigatory work and viewpoints into the future of EOSC / EU infrastructure investments, and thus requires additional consideration.

A total of 48 participants were interviewed [Name (site)]:

- David Ford (Swansea University / SAIL),
- Simon Thompson (Swansea University / SAIL),
- Richard Hier (Swansea University / SAIL),
- Cynthia Mcnerny (Swansea University / SAIL),
- Sharon Heys (Swansea University / SAIL),
- Peter Clarke (STFC / IRIS),
- Juan Bicarregui (STFC / EOSC-Pilot),
- Ian Collier (STFC / WLCG),
- Gordon Brown (STFC / SID),

- Gergely Sipos (EGI / ESOC-Hub),
- Enol Fernández (EGI / ESOC-Hub),
- Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub),
- Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub),
- David Ocana (EMBL-EBI, the 'European Node' of ELIXIR),
- Jerry Lanfear (ELIXIR Hub),
- Jennifer Harrow (ELIXIR Hub)
- Paul Calleja (Cambridge Research Computing),
- Wojciech Turek (Cambridge Research Computing),
- Jeffrey Salmond (Cambridge Research Computing),
- Jon ? (Cambridge Research Computing / StackHPC)
- Matt Davies (UCL / SES & Thomas),
- Karen Stoneham (UCL / SES & Thomas),
- Louise Chisholm (UCL / SES & Thomas),
- Thierry Sengstag (SPHN),
- Heinz Stockinger (SPHN),
- Kevin Sayers (SPHN),
- Tim Bell (CERN),
- Jakub Moscicki (CERN),
- Xavier Espinal Curull (CERN),
- Shawn Murphy (Boston Partners / ACT & SHRINE),
- Vivian Gainer (Boston Partners / ACT & SHRINE),
- Nich Wattanasin (Boston Partners / ACT & SHRINE),
- CCDS – note names not captured.
- Sharon Geva (University of Michigan / SLATECI),
- Jeremy Hallum (University of Michigan / SLATECI),
- Bob Killen (University of Michigan / SLATECI),
- Jeffrey Sica (University of Michigan / SLATECI),
- Todd Raeker (University of Michigan / SLATECI),
- Kirby ? (University of Michigan / SLATECI)
- Jing ? (University of Michigan / SLATECI)
- Derek Leydig (Penn State University)
- Matthew Craig (Penn State University)
- Wayne Figurelle (Penn State University)
- David Hancock (Indiana University / Jetstream),
- Craig Stewart (Indiana University / Jetstream),
- J. Mike Lowe (Indiana University / Jetstream),
- George Turner (Indiana University / Jetstream), and
- Abhinav Thota (Indiana University / Jetstream)

Analysis and/or Emerging Themes

1. Domains expect more than cloud in the federation

The dominantly domain-centric sites were:

- genomics – ELIXIR, SPHN & Galaxy on JetStream
- high energy physics – CERN, WLCG & IRIS
- medical – SAIL, SPHN & SHRINE/ACT

A sustainable role for coordinated domains is to develop data-standards, tools and pipelines to enable their research community to join data to analytics / processing. The advent of cloud has liberated researchers from the resource and design limitations of traditional HPC / HTC, and enabled increased CI/CD and cloud-nativeness. However, just as expanding lanes on a freeway ultimately introduces more traffic, domains naturally seek to enable pipelines across all resource types. That is, domains require **federations** that span more than just the Research Cloud, but also:

- HPC / HTC for simulation / modelling & data processing
- storage
- other clouds

Subsequently, domains are increasingly developers of software. This software increasingly takes the form of “APIs” rather than filesystems for the purposes of data connectivity. They increasingly package processing into containers, moving the processing to the data.

Domains developing such environments, are ultimately seeking a globe’s worth of researchers to adopt their data-standards, tools and pipelines. However, it is impractical for a coordinated domain to be the custodian of the globe’s worth of capacity for those researchers. Hence, there is a sense of ensuring infrastructure provider is a choice. The choice includes to be free from vendor lock, and other forms of academic freedom. Subsequently higher-level infrastructure platforms, those that significantly ease and facilitate portability such as Kubernetes, are almost ubiquitously being adopted. Logically coordinated domains are supportive of commercial clouds, as they then enable a world’s worth of researchers to pay for themselves.

However, coordinated domains are also increasingly custodians (or aiding their community members to being custodians) of their own capacity. The rationale being

- the inevitability of needing resource at many infrastructure providers and across many modalities (first point above – don't know a priori where is best),
- in making tools for global consumption, ensuring their own contributing stakeholders have sufficient resource to compete with the world (a corollary to the second point above),
- promulgating research governance over what is ultimately research infrastructure,
- enabling for increased investment by leveraging many and geographically / jurisdictionally distinct research members

2. World-class hard infrastructure sites are multi-modal & multi-domain

Given the emergence of coordinated domain-driven platforms that are increasingly agnostic to hard infrastructure providers, is what is the trend with hard infrastructure sites?

The dominantly hard infrastructure-centric sites were:

- HPC – Cambridge
- HTC – CERN, Cambridge,
- cloud – University Michigan, Jetstream

Compute and storage resource is a fuel to research. Race cars use racing fuel, which in for example Formula 1, is co-designed with the engine, to gain competitive advantage. The leading digital research infrastructures serve at least one, and increasingly more, key domains. These sites are:

- entrusted by domains to push the boundaries of technology (co-design of infrastructure to suite the domain)
- contribute to the global open source and /or vendor technologies (they are not procuring a wholly established product)
- achieve a critical mass through scale

These sites are increasingly multi-modal, in that they provide HPC, HTC, storage, and/or cloud. The leading sites are driving the accessibility of research co-design by contributing to open source infrastructure software, such as:

- CERN – Ceph, OpenStack and Kubernetes (and a host of software / middleware platforms)
- Cambridge – OpenStack for bare-metal HPC, and HPC-as-a-service
- University of Michigan - Kubernetes

3. Research infrastructure programs are still investing

The Nectar Research Cloud was a response to a national investment to increase cross-organisational collaboration. The infrastructure itself was intentionally distributed and federated, where the national capacity served the purpose of lowering barriers to the technical and cultural change (accelerating the transformation / transformation-driven). This is distinct from merely funding compute resource (capacity-driven), whether it be for cloud, HPC or HTC. However, with success, not only is there demand for more capacity to accommodate more researchers / domains / applications, those already transformed require the existing capacity to be sustained and increased.

Noting that Nectar / ARDC is not the traditional capacity-driven investment within the NCRIS ecosystem, but it has been a transformation-driven investment, and that a refresh of the existing hard infrastructure is imminent, what is the purpose of the refreshed capacity and a potential growth in capacity? When asking sites with regard to the direction of funding for capacity, the long-standing sites are asking the funders “why” – what is the capacity for?

The *why* is evolving from “*accelerating cloud*” to “***accelerating more of the right modality***”:

- when a common substrate is achieved (e.g. the CERN “grid”, promulgated and matured by the high-energy physics community by WLCG, promulgated and matured for all domains by EGI), funders are assured of quality / quality assurance of their investments, and know that a distribution of dispersion of investment will contribute to rather than compete with all other investments. For the Research Cloud, this is Core Services operating the federation of OpenStack cells. A Core Services capability needs to continue. The opportunity is to replicate its impact higher up the food chain (e.g. Kubernetes, Jupyter, VDIs) and/or across modalities (storage, HPC and HTC).
- given the above, funders are increasingly focussing the critical mass of their own investments on fewer world-class sites that innovate & scale (lead and make accessible their contributions for others)
- entrain best-practices throughout many stakeholder sites, and thus achieve the necessary capacity through co-investment. This scales from domains attracting their own co-investment for capacity, to the major contributors (as per the point above), to the long-tail of institutions.
- bridging the gap between resource intensive domains and data sensitivity. E.g EGI’s Federated IT Service Management, ISO27k, etc.

This is perhaps captured by statement from Peter Clarke (IRIS) – “It is hard for a central agency can capture the hearts and minds of research communities, hence a bottom up approach”.

Another *why* to accelerate more of the right behaviour:

- drive research and research infrastructure to be cloud-native & CI/CD, and thus in-line with the major ICT movements

The key examples are:

- EGI and the role of the EOSC-Hub investment,
- the long-standing CERN and WLCG ecosystem,
- the emerging EMBL Embassy and ELIXIR ecosystem,
- the rationale to the Jetstream renewal bid

4. Sensitive / confidential data & GDPR

The sensitive data federations were:

- the set of SeRP enabled UK-wide safe havens, that began with SAIL as the access point to analysis of NHS data
- the SPHN initiative to also link health data across Switzerland, including genomics, etc.
- the ACT/SHRINE initiative, which in recognising linking data across jurisdictions and organisations is an expensive affair, provide the coordination and tools to explore for cohorts across these federations (low hanging fruit – federate to explore rather than process)

Most of the jurisdictions we visited (the United Kingdom – England and Wales, Switzerland and the EU more broadly) traditionally have strong information governance with respect to health and social data. Increasingly research in these domains require the methods and capacity available to the non-sensitive data domains. Hence most sites and funding agencies are now investing at this join point.

Swansea stated – “Solving for Australia (a federation) means solving for the world”, noting that the hierarchy of federation of states with independent health and social data governance, is unique to Australia and to some degree Canada, but in solving this it here will provide the solution for the EU.

Other growth areas: Jupyter notebooks for long-tail data-science and the transformation towards the provenance of data analysis (when combined with git, etc) and AI/ML.

5. The world reverses the ecosystem we have

“All the work Sam / Nectar / ARDC was doing helped us to understand OpenStack would scale” – CERN

“Nectar / Monash was first to push HPC and GPUs on OpenStack. Whereas Monash started with OpenStack and then did HPC, Cambridge has done it vice-versa” – Cambridge

“We’re missing a core services to service and encapsulate all the institutions we’re helping” - Jetstream

“(Core Services is a great example of loosely but sufficiently aligned and does not mandate any more than it has to. A loose approach is beneficial for the intention of maximising co-investment. Each jurisdiction can best choose their technical and social/business architectures.” Ian Collier

Appendix 1 - Panel members brief biographies

Name and Contact	Brief biography
Global experiences digital research infrastructure federations panel members	
Dr Steve Quenette steve.quenette@monash.edu +61 438 558 275	Dr Steve Quenette is the Deputy Director of the Monash eResearch Centre, and the lead of the Monash node of the Australian (Nectar) Research Cloud & Research Data Services. His role within Monash University is to lead and drive the adoption of digital technology and advanced techniques in all fields of research. He has vast experience in business strategy, technology strategy, transformation and operations, with experiences ranging from universities, defence, hospitals and startups. He has a Phd in computer science, a Bch Science and a Bch Engineering. He has also participated in several applied domains of research including the biological sciences, healthcare, geophysics and energy. Steve has developed his present team to be global pioneers of software defined infrastructure, ranging from networks to clouds to domain-specific to federated platforms. He has long-standing partnerships with technology leaders and integrators.
Dr J Max Wilkinson max.wilkinson@ardc.edu.au +64 27 747 4890	Dr Wilkinson is an independent consultant providing services to the research data management, research data governance and research infrastructure domains. For the last 5 years he has provided services to numerous eResearch organisations in Australasia including the National eScience Infrastructure (NeSI), Council of New Zealand Research Librarians (CONZUL), AgResearch, eResearch 2020, MBIE, the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and Microscopy Australia. Prior to this he worked in the UK, most recently as Head Of Research Data and Network Services at University College London, the Datasets Programme Manager at the British Library and Informatics Coordinator at the NCRI. He received his PhD in Molecular Nephrology from UCL in 2003 and is a PRINCE2 certified project manager.
Brendan Davey brendan.davey@utas.edu.au +61 412 917 705	Brendan Davey is the Acting Director of the Tasmanian Partnership for Advanced Computing (TPAC). TPAC provides eResearch services to local and interstate partners, and is a node of both the NeCTAR research cloud and Research Data Services. Brendan oversees the day to day delivery of eResearch services ensuring current and future eResearch needs are met. He has extensive experience in delivering ICT services in higher education and delivering multisite global ICT solutions in the commercial sector. He has been working in the eResearch sector for the past seven years and has managed many projects, many for the marine research community including the Marine Virtual Laboratory (MARVL), and numerous Australian National Data Services (ANDS) projects. He has a background in computer science and electronics. He is certified in ISO 27001 Information Security, BS25999 Business Continuity Management, Prince 2 and ITIL.
Machine learning infrastructure deployed at scale: understanding requirements, demand, impact and international best practice panel members	
Dr Wojtek Goscinski wojtek.goscinski@monash.edu +61 412 133 156	Dr Wojtek James Goscinski is Associate Director at the Monash eResearch Centre, a role in which he leads teams to develop and implement digital strategies to nurture and underpin high-impact research. He is the coordinator of MASSIVE (www.massive.org.au), a national high performance computing facility for data analysis, and the manager of the Characterisation Virtual Laboratory (www.cvl.org.au), an Australia program to connect scientific instruments with computing infrastructure. He holds a PhD in Computer Science, a Bachelor of

	Design and a Bachelor of Computer Science and Software Engineering.
<p>Komathy Padmanabhan komathy.padmanabhan@monash.edu [Some parts of the USA tour only] +61 424 711 587</p>	<p>Komathy Padmanabhan is the Data Science and AI platform manager at Monash University. In her role as the Establishment Manager, Komathy is responsible for developing foundational Strategy, Business and Operations model of the Data Science and AI platform. She has vast experience in Strategic planning, business architecture, Business-IT strategic alignment and Business performance management across multiple domains. Komathy holds Masters of Business Administration (in Strategic Management) and Bachelors in Information Technology.</p>
<p>Developing a proposal for enabling the creation of health data collections and a federated secure platform for research collaborations over these collections of sensitive data panel members</p>	
<p>Anitha Kannan anitha.kannan@monash.edu [UK part of tour only] +61 409 926 465</p>	<p>Anitha Kannan is the Director, Research Platform Data Strategy in the Office of the Vice-Provost, Research and Research Infrastructure. Her role is focused on establishing and delivering a comprehensive data strategy for the Monash Technology Research Platforms in order to realise the full potential of the University's research infrastructure. This strategy encompasses technologies, processes and capabilities developed within the University and through strategic partnerships with national/international institutions, industry and government. She was instrumental in establishing Helix, which is a core capability supporting health researchers, the largest research cohort at the University, with health data infrastructure and informatics expertise. Prior to this, she was a part of the leadership team at the Monash eResearch Centre. This followed a 14 year stint in the IT industry with product development and IT services organisations like Hewlett Packard and Texas Instruments. She holds a Bachelor of Engineering in Electronics and Communication.</p>
<p>OpenStack Scientific Interest Group panel members</p>	
<p>Stig (Stephen) Telfer stig@telfer.org +44 7968 770721 [some UK sites only]</p> <p>and/or</p> <p>John Taylor john@stackhpc.com +447736778093 [some UK sites only]</p>	<p>Stig has a background in R&D working for various prominent technology companies, particularly in HPC and software-defined networking. Stig is now CTO for StackHPC, a consultancy specialising in the convergence of cloud, HPC and big data. Stig is also co-chair of the OpenStack Scientific Special Interest Group, a globally-distributed grouping of research institutions using OpenStack for research computing use cases.</p> <p>John has been involved with HPC for over 30 years and witnessed the move away from proprietary Supercomputers to today's HPC commodity clusters. Most recently he co-founded StackHPC Ltd. to promote the convergence of HPC with cloud through the use and development of OpenStack within Research Computing. Previous to this John has worked in technical marketing, sales and project management for various HPC system and technology component suppliers. While at StackHPC, John has also been part of the Square Kilometre Array Science Data Processor management and design teams, under the aegis of the University of Cambridge. For the SKA, he worked on systems engineering artefacts and architecture definition and jointly led prototyping activities for large scale storage data challenges.</p>

Appendix 2 - Site member brief biographies

Name and Contact	Brief biography
Swansea / SAIL	
David V Ford	<p>Professor of Health Informatics</p> <p>David is Professor of Health Informatics at Swansea University's College of Medicine, where he is Principal investigator and Director of the Administrative Data Research Centre Wales (ADRCW), a £13million investment into Wales by the ESRC as part of its Big Data initiative. David is the principal investigator and Director of the Multiple Sclerosis Register, a UK facility to collect patient-donated data and link it to clinical and administrative data, in order to support research and better service planning.</p> <p>David is joint lead of the SAIL Databank, an internationally recognised data linkage resource that safely and securely share linked and carefully de-identified data from a wide variety of routinely collected data from across Wales, and which supports a wide range of researchers from across the UK and internationally. David is also responsible for the development and the use of Swansea's Secure e-Research Platform (SeRP), which is increasingly used by researchers and data custodians around the world to safely curate and share the data.</p> <p>David is also deputy Director of the Substantive Health Data Research UK (HDRUK) site for Wales and Northern Ireland, working with other national experts in HDRUK to develop way health data can be used to improve health, healthcare and medicine.</p> <p>David is Co-Investigator on numerous other research grants including Healthwise Wales, Challenging Human Environments and Research Impact for a Sustainable and Healthy Digital Economy (CHERISH-DE) and National Centre for Mental Health (NCMH).</p> <p>David is a member of numerous committees and national bodies relating to health informatics and health-related research. He has received research grants and consultancy contracts valuing over £60m over recent years. Professor Ford was Director of the International Population Data Linkage Network 2014-2016.</p>
Simon Thompson	<p>Simon is the Director of Technology for Population Data Sciences at Swansea University. He has over 20 years of NHS and academic experience and is the Systems Architect for the Secure e-Research Platform (SeRP). Simon has overseen the design, development and depolyment of SeRP technology worldwide and manages a highly skilled and diverse team of 20 developers and system administrators. Simon also leads the innovation, design, development and implementation of all SAIL technical system developments. He is responsible for delivering the technical workstream for Swansea as part of the UK network of health e-research centres of excellence. His areas of expertise include NHS systems architecture and development, networking, security and VMWare. Simon is a registered BSc Software Engineer, a Microsoft Certified Engineer, a registered PRINCE2 practitioner and a registered SCRUM Master.</p>
Sharon Heys	<p>Sharon is a qualified and practising Solicitor with over fifteen years post qualification experience in data protection law within the UK and European context. She has a wealth of experience in both private and public sectors and has worked with all aspects of data management and information governance including policy and contract drafting, breach reporting and data mapping. Sharon has advised academics and cyber security professionals on niche and complex areas of advice and has coordinated with leading counsel on issues of compliance and legality. In her current role she acts as Head of Litigation and Due Diligence to the Population Data Science Department of Swansea University.</p>

Cynthia Mcnerney	<p>Cynthia McNerney is the Head of Data Acquisition and Provisioning for SAIL. She is responsible for all aspects of governance and management of data coming into SAIL from external organisations, both in relation to managing existing data held by SAIL and negotiating new datasets to be shared.</p> <p>She manages the whole process of bringing data into SAIL, including agreement to share, the technical processes of loading and linking data, and ongoing assurance that the terms and conditions of sharing are consistently met. She is also responsible for leading on SAIL's Information Governance Review Panel process.</p>
Richard Hier	<p>Richard is the SeRP Programme Manager with 15 years experience of NHS and private sector IT implementation. In his role as Programme Manager at Data Sciences, Richard manages the relationships between organisations using the Swansea developed Secure Electronic Research Platform (SeRP) across the UK and globally. Reporting to Simon Thompson, Richard coordinates the activities of the 20 strong team of developers and system administrators at Swansea.</p> <p>Richard is a registered PRINCE2 practitioner and holds ITIL, MSP and other best practice qualifications.</p>
STFC / IRIS	
Peter Clarke	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
STFC / EOSC-Pilot	
Juan Bicarregui	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
STFC / WLCG	
Ian Collier	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
STFC / SID	
Gordon Brown	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
EGI / EOSC-Hub	
Gergely Sipos	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Enol Fernández	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
ELIXIR	
Jen Harrow	<p>Tools Platform Coordinator</p> <p>Jen Harrow holds an Mphil from Sussex University, and a PhD in Plant Sciences from Cambridge University. Working closely with the Tools Platform leadership team, Jen plays a key role in aligning the development of ELIXIR Tools and Services Registry with other ELIXIR services. Jen also drives ELIXIR benchmarking</p>

	strategy and facilitates collaboration with other ELIXIR Platforms and Communities. Formerly, Jen worked at Illumina, where she was Program Manager for Population Genomics, primarily involved in collaborating with Genomics England to develop an Interpretation Platform for Cancer and Rare Disease. Prior to this, she was leading the GENCODE project at the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute, producing the curated human and mouse reference gene sets.
Jerry Lanfear	Chief Technical Officer Jerry leads on the ELIXIR-wide technical strategy, and oversees developments across the five ELIXIR Platforms (Data, Tools, Interoperability, Compute and Training). Working with ELIXIR Members and international partners, Jerry brings together scientific and technical expertise and resources for the development of ELIXIR's portfolio of bioinformatics services. Prior to joining ELIXIR, Jerry works at Pfizer where he was a Senior Director within the IT group with responsibility for IT service delivery across R&D within the UK and for data management globally.
Corinne Martin	External Relations Officer (Impact & International) Corinne is responsible for ELIXIR's international strategy, and its positioning and visibility with funders and policy-makers. She also supports ELIXIR Nodes in Member Countries in demonstrating the socio-economic impacts of their activities, and bioinformatics in general, in the health, food security, and environmental sectors. Prior to joining ELIXIR, Corinne worked at the science-policy interface (United Nations Environment World Conservation Monitoring Centre), and as a spatial ecologist and fisheries biologist in the UK, France and Greece. She is passionate about making data relevant to, and useable by, decision-makers of various sectors.
Jonathan Tedds	Compute Platform Coordinator <i>(still to be provided)</i>
David Ocana	Cloud Engineer - Systems applications, EMBL-EBI <i>(still to be provided)</i>
Cambridge Research Computing	
Paul Calleja	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Wojciech Turek	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Jeffrey Salmond	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Jon ?	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
UCL / SES & Thomas	
Matt Davies	Based within the Office of the Vice-Provost (Research) at UCL, Matt Davis is Director of Research Coordination & Planning for UCL's BEAMS School, comprising the Faculties of Built Environment, Engineering Sciences, and Mathematical & Physical Sciences. Leading a team of research facilitators and coordinators he is responsible for the strategic coordination and development of research and research funding across the School. He serves as UCL's Operational Lead for the Science & Engineering South (SES) consortium, a partnership of UCL, King's College London, Imperial College London, Queen Mary University of

	<p>London, and the Universities of Cambridge, Oxford and Southampton. Matt joined UCL in 2011, moving from Engineering & Physical Sciences Research Council, where he was a member of EPSRC's Research Infrastructure programme. He has more than 12 years' experience working in research administration, policy and strategy. Matt joined UCL in 2011, moving from Engineering & Physical Sciences Research Council and has a PhD in materials science from EPFL, Switzerland.</p>
Karen Stoneham	<p>Materials Research, and High Performance Computing Centre (HPC) Coordinator, with 12 years' experience working in the higher education sector, preceded by a decade in the public sector. A background in general Operational Management (event delivery, research management, financial, website management, marketing, and secretarial).</p> <p>Since 2013, Karen Stoneham has supported high-level materials research academics at two virtual centres; the Materials Research Institute at Queen Mary UoL (QMUL), and presently at the Thomas Young Centre, and Materials and Molecular Modelling Hub, at University College London (UCL). Prior to this, Karen supported Business, and Physics PhD students through their studies, at Brunel University and QMUL respectively.</p>
Louise Chisholm	<p>Louise Chisholm joined UCL in 2015 as a Strategic Research Coordinator in the Office of the Vice-Provost (Research). She is part leadership team for the UCL eResearch Domain (eRD) which supports the UCL community, across all faculties, who use data and computational sciences and digital technologies as a methodology in their research. The eRD develops strategies and initiatives to foster an environment in which researchers, using these technologies, flourish. The eRD steering committee provides academic oversight of the Research IT Services department's capital budget. Louise recently led the development of UCL's Research Data Strategy. She also develops high-quality funding applications, interdisciplinary communities, and creates opportunities for researchers to improve their technical skills. Louise has more than 9 years' experience in programme management, developing industry-academic partnerships and strategy. She has a PhD from Oxford University and undertook a postdoctoral fellowship at the Max Planck Institute of Epigenetics and Immunology, Germany.</p>
SPHN	
Thierry Sengstag	<p>Dr Thierry Sengstag is associate director of sciCORE, the scientific computing center at University of Basel, Switzerland and a platform of SIB – Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. He coordinates the three service axes of the center: high-performance computing, data management and data analysis. He is head of node in the project BioMedIT, started in 2017, supporting the Swiss Personalized Health Network initiative. Before joining Basel in 2013, he has notably established the bioinformatics service unit of RIKEN Yokohama's sequencing center (2010-2013) and had a leading role in the EU FP6 project ACGT (Advancing Clinico-Genomics Trials on Cancer, 2006-2010). He holds a PhD in computational physics (2001).</p>
Heinz Stockinger	<p>Dr. Heinz Stockinger is currently leading the Core-IT group of the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics being in charge of managing compute and storage infrastructure for scientific and sensitive data. Heinz is the coordinator of one of these BioMedIT nodes in Switzerland. Within the Swiss Personalized Health Network, he was leading the IT security working group taking care of the Information Security Policy and corresponding training. Previously, he was SIB's Chief Technology Officer managing web applications and other internet technologies. Prior to joining SIB in 2006 he had several technical and management functions at CERN, Switzerland, and SLAC, USA. He has a Ph.D. in</p>

	Computer Science and a venia docendi from the University of Vienna, Austria.
Kevin Sayers	Kevin Sayers is a member of the Personalized Health Informatics (PHI) group of the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. The PHI group is responsible for coordinating activities within Swiss Personalized Health Network (SPHN). In this role he leads the BioMedIT Interoperability Working Group. This group works to identify and provide solutions to SPHN researchers which enable their analysis workflows across BioMedIT nodes. This includes the assessment and deployment of containerization, workflow manager, and federated compute technologies.
CERN	
Tim Bell	<p>Tim Bell is responsible for the compute and monitoring group in the IT department at CERN, the European Laboratory for Particle Physics, which manages the infrastructure for 13,000 physicists around the world to support fundamental research. He previously worked as a Unix kernel developer at IBM along with managing large scale Unix production deployments and services for Deutsche Bank in Europe. Tim holds a Bachelors in Computer Science from Cambridge University UK.</p> <p>His team is running the CERN OpenStack cloud which has been in production since July 2013 and is currently around 320,000 cores. This cloud provides processing power to analyse the data from the Large Hadron Collider and other experiments along the compute resources for the lab.</p> <p>Tim has been an elected individual director of the OpenStack Foundation management board since 2012 and was a founding member of the OpenStack user committee and served from 2013-2015.</p>
Jakub Moscicki	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Xavier Espinal Curull	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Boston Partners / ACT & SHRINE	
Shawn Murphy	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Vivian Gainer	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Nich Wattanasin	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Boston Partners / CCDS	
University of Michigan / SLATECI synopsis	
Sharon Geva	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Jeremy Hallum	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Bob Killen	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Jeffrey Sica	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Todd Raeker	<i>(still to be provided)</i>

Kirby	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Jing ?	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Penn State University	
Derek Leydig	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Matthew Craig	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Wayne Figurelle	<i>(still to be provided)</i>
Indiana University / Jetstream	
David Hancock	<p>Director – Advanced Cyberinfrastructure, Research Technologies Primary Investigator – Jetstream David Hancock is the director for advanced cyberinfrastructure in IU's Research Technologies division. Hancock is responsible for directing IU's local and national high performance computing (HPC), storage, and cloud resources for research. Hancock is the primary investigator for the Jetstream project funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF). He is also responsible for directing IU system administrators who participate in the NSF XSEDE and Wrangler projects.</p> <p>Hancock is an active member in multiple HPC community organizations and currently a member on the board of the Cray User Group where he has served as president and vice president. Hancock is also an elected member of the XSEDE Advisory Board, and a representative in the XSEDE Service Provider (SP) Forum. Previously he served as the vice president for the IBM HPC User Group (SPXXL) and vice chair of the XSEDE SP Forum.</p>
Craig Stewart	<p>Executive Director – IU Pervasive Technology Institute Download Dr. Craig Stewart has been the executive director of the Indiana University Pervasive Technology Institute (PTI) since 2005. PTI is Indiana University's flagship organization for research and development in cyberinfrastructure, informatics, and computer science in support of science and engineering research, artistic creativity, and cybersecurity. Stewart's personal research focus is in advanced computing architectures, particularly the optimal use and mix of high-performance computing (supercomputing) and cloud computing to address problems in data analysis and simulation. Stewart is one of the top researchers in the world on the topic of return on investment in advanced cyberinfrastructure.</p> <p>Stewart has been involved in advanced computing since writing Fortran-based statistical applications while completing his Ph.D. in biology in the 1980s. From 1996 to 2017, Stewart was responsible for all aspects of IU's supercomputer and research software services and operations. From 2005 to 2017, Stewart was Associate Dean for Research Technologies and, as such, was responsible for all central supercomputers, data storage systems, and visualization systems.</p> <p>Stewart has been the principal investigator for or the primary writer of grant proposals bringing more than \$200M in funding to Indiana University. Stewart was the founding PI of Jetstream, the first cloud computing system funded by the National Science Foundation for production use by the general science and</p>

	<p>engineering community in the U.S. Jetstream now serves thousands of researchers and students.</p> <p>Stewart’s career objective is to enable the Indiana University Pervasive Technology Institute and University Information Technology Services to deliver useful and innovative services—in support of scientific, scholarly, and artistic accomplishment; education; and economic development—to Indiana University, the State of Indiana, the United States, and other democratic countries in ways that benefit all of these constituencies and the world as a whole.</p> <p>Stewart holds a PhD in ecology and evolutionary biology from Indiana University, and a BA in mathematics and biology from Wittenberg University.</p>
<p>J. Mike Lowe</p>	<p>Mike Lowe has worked in high performance computing and virtualization for thirteen years at Indiana University. A Purdue University graduate in computer engineering he has experience in operating systems, chip, and embedded design. At Indiana University he was responsible for the operation of four HPC systems. Having built and run two virtualized hosting systems for science gateways, he now is the architect of Indiana University’s Jetstream project funded by the National Science Foundation.</p>
<p>George Turner</p>	<p>George Turner is the Chief Systems Architect for the Research Technologies Division of Indiana University's University Information Technologies Services and the associated Pervasive Technologies Institute. Turner has worked for nearly four decades in scientific, research, and engineering fields and has in-depth experience in the photographic, astronomical, and particle physics communities. Turner has actively worked on real-time data acquisition systems, analysis of data products produced by these systems as well as experimental and theoretical scientific workflows. For the past twenty years, Turner has worked with the High Performance Systems group which is responsible for Indiana University's cloud based and high performance research computing systems. This group is responsible for the delivery of research computing services to users including the faculty, students, and staff of Indiana University, government and business users from around the state of Indiana, and a national & international user base accessing federally funded resources hosted at Indiana University.</p>
<p>Abhinav Thota</p>	<p>Abhinav Thota is a Senior Technical Lead in the Research Applications and Deep Learning team in the Research Technologies center at the Pervasive Technology Institute, Indiana University. The RADL team helps users efficiently use the supercomputing resources at IU. They handle user support, software licensing, installation & modules, and support a linux remote desktop service. Abhinav has a master's degree in Systems Science from LSU.</p>